

IMPLEMENTATION OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION IN DARUT TAQRIB SHIA ISLAMIC BOARDING SCHOOL

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Abstract

Several incidents of violence related with the Shia community that occurred in Sampang, Semarang, and several places issued stereotypes, negative attitudes, unbalanced views are attached to the Shia, sometimes even considered heretical. Like it or not, Shia is part of Islam. As part of Islam, the Shiites also have educational institutions that are characteristic of Islam, namely Islamic boarding schools. Education is the first task of prophetic duty with the first revelation of iqra. The famous Shia Islamic boarding school in Central Java is located in two districts, Jepara district and Pekalongan district. One of them is Darut Taqrib Islamic Education in Jepara. This study aim to find out about Islamic education in the Shia Islamic Boarding School. This research is a qualitative, with case study approach. The data of this research obtained through interviews, observation, and document studies. Analysis in this research using the interactive models of Miles and Hubberman. The results of the study showed that education at the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School used sorogan, bandongan, and wetonan learning methods. Indonesian language used to explain the contents of kitab kuning, the graduation of students based on ethics and competence is not based on time of learning.

Keywords: Islamic Education, Shia, Darut Taqrib, and Islamic Boarding Schools

Introduction

Many people think that Shia is an Islamic group that deviates from the majority. The Shia incident in Bangil in 2007 and in several places in East Java (Saefudin and Rohman, 2018: 51) further strengthened this stigma. Shia in Central Java, especially in Jepara, became known to the public a year after the Iranian revolution in 1979. Since the 1980s the Shia community has attracted a lot of attention. Stereotypes, negative attitudes, and unpleasant reactions are carried by this community (Elizabeth, 2009: 115).

Shia in Indonesia have several large and modern printers to publish Shia books (Jaiz, 2005: 5-10), it also has many educational institutions, one of which is the Darut Taqrib Islamic boarding school in Jepara. Shia (Yumitro, 2017: 237) build their own concept that regulates the system so that it is always in accordance with Shia interests. They introduced the concept of wilayat al faqih which tried to combine the concept of

democracy with religious foundations according to what they understood. Its implementation in Iran is known as the state form of the Islamic Republic of Iran after the 1979 revolution.

Shia in their journey is also known as Ahlul-Bayt, a name that is illuminating, noble, eternal, and is the name most loved by someone who claims to love Muhammad Rasulullah (Fanani, 1991: 15-20). The main characteristic that is used as a benchmark that someone is a Shia adherent is the statement that Sayyidina Ali bin Abi Talib is an Imam in the religious field and at the same time as the head of state after Muhammad Rasulullah died (Shihab, 2007: 27). This is not an exaggeration if it is analogous to the inheritance system that applies in Arabia, that those who can become heirs are descendants of the male lineage, not from the parents-in-law or daughter-in-law.

Historically, the emergence of Shia in Indonesia coincided with the first entry of Islam into the archipelago. The arrival of the Shia refers to the theory of the spread of Islam in Indonesia that Islam that came to Indonesia was Sunni Islam. However, then Shia entered Indonesia through tarekat schools. This can be seen in the Qadiriyyah-Naqsbandiyyah tarekat whose genealogy is continued to the Shia priests. In the lineage, the first seven or eight were Shia imams. as illustrated: from Allah, the Angel Gabriel, the Messenger of Allah, Ali, Husayn, Ali bin Husain, continued to the Shia Imam until Imam Ali Rida (Sulaiman, 2017: 19-36). The difference in teachings between Shia and Sunni is a natural one, as is the difference between the Shafi'i madhhab and the other three madhhabs. Shia and have many teachings in common. Therefore, Abdurrahman Wahid stated that culturally NU is Shia and what distinguishes it is the issue of Imamah (interview with Ustadz Miqdad November 2018). The issue of Imamah is one of the sources of the "division" between Sunnis and Shiites.

The development of wilayat al faqih also applies in the field of education. Iran is the main and even mandatory destination for students who have completed their education at Shia Islamic boarding schools in Central Java. Jepara is one of the districts where there are two places where Shia spreads, namely Bangsri and Jepara. The Islamic boarding school that has the characteristics of Shia in Bangsri is the Al-Khairat Islamic Boarding School (Sulaiman, 2017), the first caregiver of this pesantren was Abdul Qadir Bafaqih who openly stated that he was a Shia adherent (Elizabeth, 2009: 130). This statement of shifting from Sunni to Shia has consequences for the santri, some still survive and follow the understanding of the teacher, and some move from the pesantren leaving the teacher.

The education that prevails in Shia has a special characteristic. This education is based on the life of the Prophet Muhammad and his family which is very full of advice, teachings, and guidance for all mankind (Alkaf, no date). The Prophet educated his companions with special education

sourced from the Koran (Abidin, 2012: 23-30). The concept of education that comes from the Qur'an, the hadith of the Prophet SAW and the hadith of the Imams of Ma'shum aims to create *insān al-kāmil* (Al-Kailani, 1987: 253) or perfect humans in the future. In this concept, education starts from pre-pregnancy to when the child is going through his teenage years.

Shia chose the form of *pesantren* as an institution for the development and dissemination of their religious understanding. The position of *pesantren* is very vital in the development of Islamic education (Muqoyyidin, 2013: 1). This can be seen in its role as a means of transforming values and culture which is internalized in the elements of the *pesantren*. On the one hand, Islamic boarding schools have a big role in the independence of the Indonesian nation and in maintaining the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

Kyai or *ustadz* become top figures in Islamic boarding school education. Kyai instills the spirit of religious spirituality and the spirit of defending the homeland (Aji, 2018: 27-52). The study seeks to identify and analyze the implementation of Islamic education conducted by the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School in Jepara. An important aspect that will be studied is regarding the process of Islamic education in this *pesantren*, including how the implementation of Islamic education is carried out at the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School?, and what values are developed in Islamic education at the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School?

Literature Review

Islamic Education in Indonesia

Based on Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, namely: education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills they need. , society, nation and state. Mujib in Rohman said that in the Qur'an the word *al-tarbiyah* is not found, but there are other terms that have the same root as it, namely *al-rabb*, *rabbayani*, *murabbi*, *yurbi*, and *rabbani* (Rohman, 2013: 279). Whereas in the hadith only the word *rabbani* is found. According to Abdul Mujib, each of these actually has a unity of meaning, although in certain contexts they have differences.

Islamic education is an effort to educate Islam or its teachings and values, so that it becomes a way of life (view of life) and one's attitude to life (Rohman, 2013: 280). In this second sense, Islamic education can take the form of: first, all activities carried out by a person or an institution to assist a person or group of students in instilling and developing Islamic teachings and values. Second, all phenomena or encounters between two

or more people whose impacts are: the implantation and or growth of Islamic teachings and values on one or several parties.

Islamic education is all efforts to maintain and make students or students able to inherit Islamic knowledge as a whole. Every intentional effort and action to achieve goals must have a good and strong foundation or foundation.

Values of Islamic Education

The values of Islamic education are sourced from the Qur'an and the hadith of the prophet. Al-Quran and hadith are sources of universal educational value. These two guidelines provide theory and best practice for Muslims. Al-Quran provides an ideal theory that is philosophical and suitable in every space and time, while the hadith provides examples of ideal and applicable practice.

The values that are carried in Islamic education are the value of exemplary, sincerity, and the use of knowledge or the benefits of knowledge. educators not only provide theories about understanding and behavior, but they also provide examples as role models (Chaeruddin B., 2013: 433). The example of a teacher is an effective way to provide examples and internalize Islamic values in students. Knowledge is not only in the mind, but is realized in everyday life (Nurul Fajriah, 2019: 120). Any knowledge given by educators must be able to become signs in the lives of educators and students.

Pesantren

Pesantren as part of Islamic educational institutions open themselves to accept the positive side of globalization (Farida, 2015: 145). History records that pesantren are able to adapt to the times (Indra, 2018: 1). Pesantren is very instrumental in the effort to educate people's lives. The emergence of pesantren in society in the 15th century could not be separated from the role of Walisongo in spreading Islam in Java (Sulistiono, 2014: 1-11). Pesantren education gave birth to tough fighters who participated in the struggle for Indonesian independence. He is included in an educational institution that continues to survive both in terms of curriculum, leadership style, and teaching methods that tend to remain unchanged. However, pesantren has proven to be able to survive and compete with other educational institutions in modern times.

Pesantren gives its own color to the face of the world of education in the country. He teaches people to be literate and culturally literate (Hasanah, 2015: 203). For the common people, admit it or not, at first they were more familiar with Arabic letters than Latin letters. Pesantren provide enough knowledge and even more to the public to be able to recognize reading and writing which at that time was an expensive and special item.

Islamic boarding schools have made at least three major contributions to education in Indonesia (Harahap and Siregar, 2017: 288). First, pesantren preserve and continue a cheap and affordable education system that favors the people. Second, Islamic boarding schools change the aristocratic education system into a democratic education system. Third, Islamic boarding schools prioritize spiritual and character education before other education.

The growth and development of pesantren is strongly influenced by the caregivers who lead it. Pesantren is the most autonomous Islamic educational institution in Indonesia that cannot be intervened by any party except with the permission of the kyai (Kesuma, 2017: 99-117). The great influence of caregivers in the community will also affect the pesantren they lead. The legitimacy of the pesantren is highly dependent on the role of a kyai in society. He is a central figure who has authority in the pesantren he leads and also the local community. The opinion of a kyai will be accepted by the santri and the community whether they know the reason or not. For those who know the reason, the support will be even greater. And for those who do not know the reason, they will assume that the kyai's knowledge is so high that they are unable to digest the kyai's thoughts.

In general, Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia recognize and cultivate the six components contained in the ta'lim muta'allim book (Syafii, 2014: 9). This book is a reference for Islamic boarding schools, both Islamic boarding schools that teach takhassush the yellow book and takhashsush Al-qur'an. Meanwhile, the current education focuses on several components that have been standardized by the government. In formal education, it is guided by eight standardized standards. The eight standards are content standards, process standards, standards, educators and education personnel, graduation standards, infrastructure standards, assessment standards, and financing standards.

The development of pesantren today leads to maintaining its existence and following the times. The classical education system has been used in grouping students' learning ages. This classical system is usually based on the competence of the santri. The ability of a student will determine the position of the student to start the lesson. So it is very possible that a striking age difference will be in the same class because they have the same competence. Seniority is not seen from the age but from the ability of the students themselves.

Islamic boarding schools in learning use the sorogan, bandongan, and wetonan methods (Arif, 2011: 139). Sorogan is a teaching method in which students advance one by one by reading the book being studied in front of the kyai, then the kyai gives a little explanation of the contents of what is read and does not know what the students mean. Second, bandongan is a teaching method in which the kyai reads the book while

providing an explanation of the *l'rab* and the meaning of the content of the book being read, while the santri listen and write the meaning or meaning of the book that is owned by the kyai. Santri write down the position of the existing sentence so that there are no different interpretations.

Education in pesantren can be seen as education that ignores differences in the quality of inputs. He accepts all prospective students in all conditions according to the capacity of the pesantren (Aji, 2018: 27). Pesantren prioritizes the output produced. In its development, pesantren has evolved in producing output (Muksin, 2016: 105). In the early days, pesantren wanted reliable preachers (Eka Putra, Styadin and Sunandar, 2016: 72). In the second period, the pesantren produced kyai who were able to manage the pesantren or teach religion to the community in which they lived. In the third period or now, Islamic boarding schools produce people who are able to compete in the field of work and religious entrepreneurs. The education process carried out traditionally is able to produce the desired quality without time constraints.

Method of Research

The research on the implementation of Islamic education in the Shia Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School in Jepara is included in qualitative research. Observation (Yusuf, 2017: 384) and the classification of pesantren became the initial process of this research. Observations were made by observing the pesantren environment which included classrooms, mosques, libraries, ustadz, and students. The research focuses on understanding the phenomena experienced by research subjects in the form of behavior, perceptions, motivations, traditions, and words holistically.

Qualitative research methods based on post positivism / interpretive philosophy, are used to examine the condition of natural objects (Anggito and Setiawan, 2018: 16). Researchers used triangulation to test the validity of the data obtained. Data analysis emphasizes meaning rather than generalization. This method seeks to reveal the various specificities inherent in individuals, groups, or communities in daily life in detail and depth that can be justified scientifically.

The research data were obtained by means of in-depth interviews (Pawito, 2007: 132-136) document studies, observations, documentation, and Focus Group Discussions (FGD). Document studies are carried out by collecting and studying documents related to the curriculum, Shia scriptures, the organizations that support them, and local policies. Data analysis uses the analysis developed by Miles and Hubberman which includes three joint activities, namely data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions (B. Miles and Hubberman, 1994: 308).

DISCUSSION

Profile of Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School Jepara

Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School Jepara is located on Jalan K.M. Thank you, Greetings Rt 05 / Rw IX Jepara Annual Krapyak. This Islamic boarding school is located in the middle of a residential area, and not far from the Ministry of Religion of Jepara Regency. Krapyak village is bordered by Potroyudan and Ayahangan villages in the north, east by Senenan and Tahunan villages, south by Mantingan village, and in the west by Karang Kebagusan village. This village is located at an altitude of 1.00 meters above sea level, by looking at this altitude, this village is included in the lowlands with an average rainfall of 100 mm.

This Islamic boarding school is located in the potroyudan, krapyak, kauman, and saripan areas which are famous for their religious population and are located in areas where the majority of nahdliyyin are. The population in this village is 11,184 consisting of 5,786 men and 5,398 women. The population based on religion consists of 11,180 Muslims, 3 Catholics, and one Hindu. There are 5 pesantren educational facilities, 25 teachers, and 550 students.

The Syi'ah Community of the Indonesian Ahlul Bait Jamaah Association (IJABI), headquartered in Kemang, Jakarta, is an interesting phenomenon about Shi'ism in Indonesia. On the other hand, there is Ahlul Bait Indonesia (ABI), a new community organization headquartered in Mampang, South Jakarta. The Jamiah Al-Mushthafa Alumni Association, abbreviated as Ikmal, has an office at the Hauzah Ilmiah Al-Mushtafa campus, Jalan Kebagusan, South Jakarta (Zuhdi, no date).

The development of Shia in Jepara and Central Java cannot be separated from Candi Village, Jepara. Shia flourished in Jepara when ustadz Abdul Ghadir Bafaqih from Tuban married a woman from Candi Village. The 1970s saw the Iranian revolution which influenced the development of Shi'ism, including in Indonesia. Ghadir also studied in Hadramaut, Yemen. In 1974, Ghadir received many shipments of books from Kuwait published by Darut Tauhid. These books talk a lot about Shia and enter into Ghadir's thoughts. Armed with these books, Ghadir talked a lot about Shia. Ghadir founded the Al-Khairat Islamic Boarding School, at the same time, Shia was declared in Jepara in 1982.

Ghadir produced several works, such as Haqqul Mubin and Muhammadun wa Akhuhu. Both works become references and sources of Shia ideology. As the hut continued to grow, the coverage of the Shia teachings brought by Abdul Ghadir was widespread. People respond normally. The first generation of Ghadir students was Ahmad Badawi. At the beginning of the establishment of the pesantren, Al-Khairat only taught Arabic, which could be the entrance to study the book. However, there were several students of Abdul Ghadir who were reported to the Military

District Command because they were considered different (<http://www.darut-taqrib.org/berita/2012/03/22/kepeacean-sunni-dan-syiah-di-jepara-1/> accessed 24 January 2019).

Miqdad Turkan, another Ghadir student, said his teacher was a Sunni. The students are also many from the Sunni community, especially Nahdlatul Ulama and Muhammadiyah. Later, said Miqdad, some of his students have remained Sunni and some have converted to Shia. Since then, Shia thrived in the Temple. The students of this pesantren are spread from various regions. As the number of santri continued to grow, news of the existence of a Shia pesantren spread.

Ghadir entered old age after ten years of managing the pesantren. He is often sick. His activity in teaching at the pesantren began to decrease. Finally, Ghadir died on August 17, 1993. He was buried in Kauman, Bangsri. Ghadir's tomb is located next to his wife's grave. Standing on a joglo-shaped building that is twice the size of a badminton court, Ghadir's tomb is always crowded with pilgrims. Since then, the activities of the pesantren have stagnated. The boarding school was closed because there was no one to take care of it.

In 1999, Ghadir's students took the initiative to establish the Darut Taqrib Islamic Foundation in Krapyak, Jepara. They don't want to see Shi'a teachings become history because there is no regeneration. In addition, at that time many Shia students had returned to study from Qum University, Iran. They are known as ahlu al-bayt.

After the Darut Taqrib foundation was established, the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School was established to accommodate students who wanted to study Shia. The pesantren was established on an area of less than one hectare. The cottage building consists of a mosque, hall or pendapa, and student rooms. In addition to establishing pesantren, Shia adherents form various forums such as the Fatimiyyah which is intended for recitation of mothers, Zainabiyyah for recitation of young women, the Ahlul Bait Youth Scientific Forum or known as FIRAB. Shia also formed the Association for Community Care in the social field.

Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School is one of the Shia educational arenas. This education is a form of regeneration (FGD with Mukhlisin, Alamsyah, Alam Firdaus, and Mualim, and Ustadz Miqdad on 27 November 2018). Currently, Darut Taqrib educates about 40 students. The students are not only from Jepara, the students also come from various provinces in Indonesia such as Lampung and East Java. There are students who only stay and some are attending public schools. Abdullah, for example, attended a vocational high school and attended a boarding school to study Shia. Miqdad stated that Shia's operational funds come from membership dues. Three areas that contributed greatly to the development of Shi'ism in Central Java, the region is one area of Pekalongan and two

places in the region of Jepara. The Shia development center is located at the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School in Jepara, Al-Khairat Jepara, and Al-hadi Pekalongan.

Research documentation 2018 : FGD with Ustadz

Implementation of Islamic education in Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School

Period of Study

Religious education in general from beginning to graduation lasts for four years. Education uses the hijri calendar. This four-year study period is the minimum study period if you want to take the boarding school graduation exam. Pesantren, in this case the ustadz and pesantren administrators, have the prerogative right to determine the graduation of students with several agreed criteria. This illustrates that the most important thing after four years of education is the competence and ability of the students, not only based on the period of study of the students.

Learning Methods and Materials

The learning carried out by Pondok Darut Taqrib is not much different from the learning given at Islamic boarding schools in general. They teach nahwu, Arabic, Aqidah, Fiqh, Usul fiqh, Mantiq, and History. The difference with Islamic boarding schools is in the goals to be achieved. Examples of material differences in the field of fiqh and Aqidah. The study of fiqh is divided into two, namely amali fiqh and Ijtihadi fiqh. Fiqh amali is fiqh that is intended for ordinary people. Lay people can directly follow amali fiqh because it is practical without knowing the reasons used by the priest.

Second, argumentative fiqh. This fiqh leads to the fiqh of ijtihad. At this level, students are equipped with fiqh knowledge related to the

comparison of schools and their methodology. Likewise, in the field of 'Aqeedah, it is also divided into two, namely aqidah which is practical and aqidah which is related to the science of kalam. Islamic boarding schools use monotheism fi shifatillah (Nubuwwah and Imamah) in the field of aqidah.

Interview with Ustadz Miqdad 29 November 2018
Researcher documentation

Third, the lessons given are based on the classical books that are the handle of the Shia scholars. Various kinds of expertise are given to the students so that they can continue to the next level in Iran. The lessons taught are aqidah, fiqh, mantiq and Arabic. Usul fiqh uses Al-manthiq Al-Mudhofar and khulashoh Mantiq.

Fourth, the background of the santri who come from various regions in Indonesia is a separate consideration for the pesantren. Pesantren wants all new students to be in the same starting position. The method used by pesantren to solve this problem is by using Indonesian in the language of instruction and giving meaning to the yellow book.

Another reason for using Indonesian is that students are less able to communicate with academics, so the use of Indonesian is important and urgent. Some pesantren use the local language, making it difficult to catch and communicate with other languages.

Educational Values Developed at Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School

The educational values used in Shia are based on the concepts that underlie the Shia group. These concepts are:

- a) Justice. Justice according to Sunni is justice according to God's logic, while justice according to Shia is justice according to God's

- logic in accordance with the laws of human logic. God will not deny human logic. Justice is a core concept in Shia.
- b) The infallibility of the Prophet Muhammad. In connection with the Prophet Muhammad, it is infallible to start before or after being sent as a prophet? In the Shia understanding, the infallibility of the prophet is attached to the prophet since before the prophethood. So, the Prophet Muhammad before and after the prophethood did not get sinned at all.
 - c) The concept of Imamah and wilayatul faqih. Imamah according to the Shia should not occur there is a break. Imamah will continue to exist from the time of the Prophet Muhammad until the end of time. The concept of Imamah that exists in the Shia can be compared to the concept of the Vatican in Rome by the Catholics. In their belief, Imamah after the Prophet Muhammad was continued by Abu Bakr As-Siddiq, Umar Bin Khotthob, Usman Bin Affan, Ali bin Abi Talib, ... to Imam Mahdi.
 - d) The concept of Imamah does not negate the territory of a country, this concept unites the ummah in one supreme religious leader who is qualified in the religious field. Imamah is different from the concept of the caliphate which is currently developing. The differences include, among others, the Khilafah abolishes territorial boundaries, the Khilafah abolishes democracy, and the Khilafah is contrary to the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. In the view of the Shia, the formation of a new state in the Shia understanding must go through a joint referendum. The real proof that Shia is supporting democracy is that Iran as the mecca is a country in the form of a republic.
 - e) Hubbul Wathon / Nationalism. Nationalism is the basis of daily learning, this is evidenced by the use of Indonesian in every book study and learning. The Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia is a fixed price for Shia / Ahlul Bait Darut Taqrib Jeparah, this is based on ideology and fatwas.
 - f) Education that develops in Shia is guided by the Book of Munyatul Pupils fi Adab Al-mufid wa Al-Mustafid. This book is a standard book used by all Shia and Ahlul Bait in the learning process. In Sunni circles this book is like the book of ta'lim Muata'alim.

Conclusion

Some groups or groups view Shia as a heretical and misleading group. However, there are also some of them who do not view them as a group outside Islam, even though there are quite a lot, simple, and serious differences between them and the majority group of Muslims, namely ahlussunnah wa al-jamaah. One of the Shi'a attitudes that are considered

less common is taqiyah. The attitude expressed by the Shia group is considered a taqiyah attitude which is indeed justified by the Shia group with certain conditions but is understood by some that it means permission to pretend or lie. This results in, no matter how compatible what the Shi'a put forward with the views of the Ahlussunnah, those who are suspicious will still judge it as an attitude of pretending or lying.

- a. The process of Islamic education carried out at the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School took place like an Islamic boarding school in general. This is because education is universal. It is only in the use of the Indonesian language that distinguishes it from other pesantren in Central Java.
- b. The values developed by Islamic education at the Darut Taqrib Islamic Boarding School are the values of justice, conscience, and the importance of the priest in education and religious life.

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- Wawancara dengan Kepala Kantor Kementerian Agama Kabupaten Jepara 28 November 2018
- Wawancara dengan Ustadz Miqdad dari Syiah yang berkenan berdiskusi dengan peneliti tanggal 29 November 2018
- Focus Discusion Groug* (FGD) dengan Ustadz Ali dan kawan-kawan yang di lingkungan Pesantren Darut Taqrib Jepara.